

Elicitation and Documentation of Explainability Requirements

Quick Reference Guide for Practitioner - One pager

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Problem

An information system might make decisions or gain results which are not directly understandable by users, weaken the user's confidence into the system. To strengthen the user's acceptance, explainability requirements will define the way rationales are communicated to users. However, the documentation of explainability requirements is still vague yet. This one-pager supports requirements engineers in the decision, whether explainability requirements are relevant for a project and if so, how these could be elicited and documented in detail.

Explainability Requirement Specification process

Follow this process:

- Identify <type of addressee>:** Representation to gain understanding of the environment and context of the stakeholder group.
- Identification of the <aspect>:** Diagram to identify the goals and sub-goals of the stakeholder group and the cognitive tasks that are performed in their environment.
- Identify the <context> and <explainer>:** Map to identify features of existing tools used by stakeholders.
- Create scenario (opt.):** Mapping to identify the scenarios that represent the processes and cognitive tasks of the stakeholder group.
- Use scenario to identify requirements:** Requirements generation through identification using interviews, prototypes, surveys and anthropomorphism studies (attribution of human essence to non-human essence entities)

Template for Documentation

As <type of addressee> I want to receive explanations about an <aspect> from an <explainer> in a <context>.

Example: As a surgeon, I want to receive explanations of an occurring error in a misbehavior or unprocessable sensor data within the SRS from a visual representation of a user interface associated with the SRS in an intuitive and understandable framework.

Element	Key Questions
<type of addressee>	Who are relevant target groups and what are their specific characteristics? What are the relevant desiderata in a particular context and are they being met? Is the information really useful/helpful for the target group?
<aspect>	Has the target group acquired a sufficient level and the right understanding to judge whether wishes are fulfilled and to facilitate their fulfillment? Is the information useful/helpful for the target group?
<context>	Are there contextual influences that hinder or promote the satisfaction of the desiderata by the explanatory process? Is the explanatory approach able to provide the right type and amount of information in an acceptable presentation? Is the information useful/helpful for the target group?
<explainer>	Als the explanation approach able to pass on the information through a suitable source that promotes the understanding of the target group? Is the information really useful/helpful for the target group?